

What did Buddha teach about the Atman? Lessons from the Sundarikasutta

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Summary:

It is often assumed that Gautama Buddha taught a philosophy absolutely counter to Vedic Sanathana Dharma. It is also assumed that he did not believe in the idea of the Atman.

By analysing a key verse in the Sundarika Sutta (Sutta Nipāta 3:4), I show that Gautama Buddha not only believed in the Atman, but also advocated core Vedic, Advaita Vedanta and Sankhya concepts found in the Vedas, Brahmanas and Upanishads.

Discussion:

One of the great lies spread about Buddhism is that it is completely disconnected from Sanathana Hindu thought. Another lie is that Gautama Buddha never accepted the idea of the Vedic Atman. Here is a Sutta that contradicts and challenges all of these assumptions.

In the Sundarika Sutta, here is what Gautama Buddha (of Kashyapa Gotra) says in Pali to a Brahmin of the Bharadwaja Gotra:¹

Anglicized Pali (original):

Māno hi te brāhmaṇa khāribhāro,
Kodho dhumo bhasmani mosavajjam;
Jivhā sujā hadayam̐ jotiṭhānam,
Attā sudanto purisassa joti.

Incorrect English translation (Bhikku Sujatho)

Conceit, brahmin, is the burden of your pack,
anger your smoke, and lies your ashes.
The tongue is the ladle, the heart the fireplace;
a well-tamed self is a person's light

Why reinterpret?

Anybody who understands Hindi can understand most of these Pali words easily. Clearly, the references to the Vedic yajna or fire-altar cannot be missed. Somehow, the sanitized translation seems disconnected from the Vedic environment which Gautama Buddha grew in.

My approach:

The problem is that it is almost impossible to find the original Pali text online. The anglicized Pali is what one can get in the Suttacentral repository. The English translations are seemingly ignorant of Vedic concepts and terminology. Hence, we see the ignorance of the translators in not understanding Vedic or Upanishad results in a sanitized English translation that seems devoid of Sanathana Hindu concepts.

Here is a close Sanskrit version I created.

Sanskrit version of Pali text:

मानः हि ते ब्राह्मण खारिभारः।

क्रोधः धूमः भस्मनि मोषदोषः।

जिह्वा स्रुव हृदयम् ज्योतिस्थानम्।

आत्मा शुद्ध अंतः पुरुषस्य ज्योतिः।

Correct English translation (My translation)

Indeed (hi), the ego (Maanam), O Brahmin, is that (te) measure (khaari) of your burden (bharo)

Anger (krodha) is smoke (dhumo) and ashes (bhasmani) that is a blocker (dosham) to Moksha

The tongue (jihva) is the sacrificial ladle (shruva) and the heart (hrdyam) is the location (sthanam) of (inner) light (jyothi)

The Atman, pure (shudh) till the end (antha), is (same as the) the light (jyoti) of the Purusha (Paramatman)

Advantages of my translation:

- 1) The translator, Bhikku Sujatho, does not understand the context, that Gautama Buddha is talking to another Brahmin. Hence, the scene is replete with Vedic imagery, which the translator, wittingly or unwittingly, misses in the translation but adds in the footnotes. For the first line, Bhikku Sujatho understands that the play of words is from Shatapatha Brahmana 11.5.6. For the second line, Bhikku Sujatho understands that the play of words is from Shatapatha Brahmana 3.7.133 and 6.6.3.10. The third line draws from the Brihadaranyaka Upanishad 4.3.7 and Rig Veda Rig Veda (1.61.5, 3.31.3, 5.1.3, 10.109.5). The fourth line draws from the Brihadaranyaka Upanishad 4.3.2. The ease with which Gautama Buddha uses Vedic and Upanishad symbolism suggests that he was well aware of all these Vedic philosophies.
- 2) The word Purusha and Atman have two meanings – a colloquial meaning and a religious meaning. For a strange reason Bhikku Bodhi has picked the common vernacular meaning instead of the religious symbolic meanings. He has interpreted “Atman” to mean “self” instead of “Paramatman,” and “Purusha” to mean “person” instead of “Paramatman.”
- 3) “Purusha” is a core Sankhya concept, which Gautama Buddha also uses. This shows his understanding of Sankhya philosophy.
- 4) Gautama Buddha talks of inner light (jyothi) and Atman one after the other. A couple of lines earlier in the same Sundarika Sutta, he says, “I’ve given up kindling firewood, brahmin, now I light only the inner flame.” All these evidence indicates that Gautama Buddha was expounding core Advaita philosophy where Atman is considered the same as Brahman (Paramatman).

- 5) The last line reads that the Atman self is the same as the Paramatman or Brahman. That unity is the final step in Moksha. This final unity is the fundamental insight of Advaita Vedanta. Hence, Buddha was only advocating basic Vedic philosophy rather than upturning it.

Divergences in my translation:

- 1) I have used Bhikku Sujatho's interpretation of "suja" as "shruva."
- 2) "Sudanto" can be interpreted as Su + Danto (good teeth) or Shudh + Anto (auspicious ending). I choose the second meaning. Bhikku Sujatho interprets the word as "well-tamed" which is not the same as mine.
- 3) "Mosavajjam" can only be approximated as Moksha Dosham. It refers to "fault of Moksha" meaning "fault that prevents one from gaining Moksha." Bhikku Sujatho interprets the word as "lies" which is different from mine.

Conclusions:

- 1) Gautama Buddha mastered and liberally quoted from the Rig Vedas, Brihadaranyaka Upanishad and the Shatapatha Brahmana. In another verse soon after, he quoted from the Katha Upanishad.
- 2) Gautama Buddha understood and adopted Sankhya philosophy.
- 3) Gautama Buddha understood and adopted the idea of the Vedic Atman.

References:

ⁱ Suttacentral source: Sundarikasutta by Bhikkhu Sujatho

<https://suttacentral.net/sn7.9/en/sujato?lang=en&layout=sidebyside&reference=none¬es=asterisk&highlight=false&script=latin>